

CYCLE: Cross-Year Contrastive Learning in Entity-Linking

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1. ADDITIONAL RESULTS - NEW ENTITIES TRAINING SET

Tables [S1](#) through Table [S7](#) present a comparison between the baseline models (BLINK and SpEL) and our model CYCLE. The dataset, "Graph-TempEL: New entities," has a training set (1,764), a validation set ($\approx 42k$, same as original TempEL dataset), and a test set ($\approx 48k$, same as original TempEL dataset). Here, the training set contains only 1,764 samples because, in the original TempEL dataset, each year's dataset contains only 1,764 'new entities' samples. Rows represent training datasets, while columns represent testing datasets. Performance evaluations for all models were based on recall metrics, specifically @1, @2, @4, @8, @16, @32, and @64.

Table S1. Results between our model and the baseline models @1 ("Graph-TempEL: New entities" as the training set).

		Test									
		2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Train											
		BLINK	2013	0.1442	0.1435	0.1430	0.1458	0.1472	0.1451	0.1432	0.1477
2014	0.1223		0.1228	0.1227	0.1234	0.1222	0.1221	0.1200	0.1260	0.1231	0.1246
2015	0.1379		0.1360	0.1373	0.1385	0.1396	0.1372	0.1373	0.1416	0.1377	0.1366
2016	0.1311		0.1321	0.1305	0.1320	0.1330	0.1304	0.1316	0.1349	0.1316	0.1326
2017	0.1405		0.1406	0.1405	0.1417	0.1430	0.1425	0.1403	0.1438	0.1413	0.1421
2018	0.1284		0.1273	0.1272	0.1268	0.1302	0.1275	0.1282	0.1305	0.1266	0.1271
2019	0.1402		0.1398	0.1419	0.1418	0.1429	0.1410	0.1409	0.1449	0.1405	0.1422
2020	0.1229		0.1231	0.1205	0.1227	0.1245	0.1225	0.1204	0.1259	0.1214	0.1237
2021	0.1269		0.1268	0.1270	0.1267	0.1272	0.1244	0.1241	0.1303	0.1295	0.1307
2022	0.1267		0.1263	0.1265	0.1274	0.1297	0.1270	0.1267	0.1317	0.1288	0.1302
SpEL	2013	0.1740	0.1735	0.1931	0.1759	0.1773	0.1950	0.1831	0.1777	0.1945	0.1933
	2014	0.1721	0.1529	0.1729	0.1735	0.1622	0.1520	0.1502	0.1760	0.1728	0.1646
	2015	0.1680	0.1659	0.1771	0.1784	0.1797	0.1873	0.1671	0.1812	0.1676	0.1866
	2016	0.1610	0.1820	0.1708	0.1821	0.1630	0.1604	0.1714	0.1749	0.1616	0.1626
	2017	0.1803	0.1804	0.1804	0.1815	0.1828	0.1724	0.1902	0.1838	0.1810	0.1722
	2018	0.1684	0.1569	0.1668	0.1568	0.1601	0.1776	0.1584	0.1806	0.1668	0.1670
	2019	0.1800	0.1697	0.1718	0.1915	0.1727	0.1811	0.1809	0.1849	0.1706	0.1924
	2020	0.1628	0.1731	0.1606	0.1728	0.1545	0.1724	0.1706	0.1661	0.1516	0.1638
	2021	0.1770	0.1567	0.1770	0.1765	0.1671	0.1643	0.1739	0.1603	0.1794	0.1705
	2022	0.1566	0.1564	0.1464	0.1475	0.1497	0.1571	0.1565	0.1613	0.1488	0.1600
CYCLE	2013	0.2198	0.2207	0.2209	0.2215	0.2249	0.2239	0.2212	0.2277	0.2246	0.2237
	2014	0.2046	0.1959	0.1942	0.1946	0.1951	0.1934	0.1935	0.1991	0.1954	0.1970
	2015	0.2121	0.2123	0.2122	0.2126	0.2125	0.2112	0.2114	0.2148	0.2115	0.2101
	2016	0.1968	0.1964	0.1964	0.1965	0.1978	0.1978	0.1957	0.1996	0.1969	0.1962
	2017	0.2009	0.1996	0.2005	0.1997	0.2018	0.1999	0.1994	0.2043	0.2004	0.2024
	2018	0.1703	0.1702	0.1680	0.1684	0.1716	0.1693	0.1698	0.1724	0.1697	0.1706
	2019	0.1994	0.1996	0.2004	0.1999	0.2027	0.1986	0.2100	0.2121	0.2192	0.2218
	2020	0.1627	0.1640	0.1634	0.1644	0.1657	0.1629	0.1621	0.1666	0.1637	0.1643
	2021	0.1944	0.1939	0.1925	0.1935	0.1940	0.1930	0.1918	0.1968	0.1952	0.1964
	2022	0.1541	0.1524	0.1535	0.1532	0.1538	0.1521	0.1624	0.1667	0.1623	0.1626

Table S2. Results between our model and the baseline models @2 ("Graph-TempEL: New entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.2133	0.2139	0.2135	0.2138	0.2159	0.2157	0.2142	0.2183	0.2137	0.2115	
	2014	0.1845	0.1850	0.1841	0.1842	0.1853	0.1841	0.1808	0.1858	0.1829	0.1860	
	2015	0.2037	0.2034	0.2062	0.2058	0.2071	0.2066	0.2053	0.2084	0.2050	0.2035	
	2016	0.1987	0.1981	0.1970	0.1986	0.1998	0.1984	0.1956	0.2009	0.1967	0.1989	
	2017	0.2102	0.2099	0.2106	0.2123	0.2132	0.2134	0.2095	0.2136	0.2112	0.2122	
	2018	0.1903	0.1912	0.1931	0.1916	0.1935	0.1917	0.1916	0.1940	0.1897	0.1917	
	2019	0.2074	0.2084	0.2108	0.2112	0.2124	0.2128	0.2088	0.2136	0.2092	0.2111	
	2020	0.1861	0.1857	0.1849	0.1854	0.1890	0.1868	0.1840	0.1894	0.1845	0.1870	
	2021	0.1910	0.1928	0.1901	0.1909	0.1915	0.1893	0.1871	0.1938	0.1948	0.1927	
	2022	0.1913	0.1917	0.1911	0.1914	0.1944	0.1909	0.1889	0.1950	0.1925	0.1935	
SpEL	2013	0.2531	0.2541	0.2536	0.2739	0.2656	0.2657	0.2541	0.2582	0.2633	0.2617	
	2014	0.2445	0.2250	0.2339	0.2340	0.2351	0.2341	0.2209	0.2358	0.2226	0.2358	
	2015	0.2435	0.2635	0.2461	0.2459	0.2472	0.2564	0.2553	0.2483	0.2548	0.2634	
	2016	0.2387	0.2483	0.2472	0.2485	0.2399	0.2483	0.2455	0.2507	0.2365	0.2490	
	2017	0.2499	0.2700	0.2503	0.2717	0.2729	0.2633	0.2592	0.2533	0.2509	0.2519	
	2018	0.2502	0.2510	0.2328	0.2516	0.2437	0.2417	0.2315	0.2442	0.2496	0.2512	
	2019	0.2473	0.2479	0.2609	0.2612	0.2623	0.2528	0.2587	0.2537	0.2692	0.2608	
	2020	0.2262	0.2255	0.2248	0.2353	0.2491	0.2271	0.2338	0.2296	0.2344	0.2471	
	2021	0.2510	0.2526	0.2500	0.2408	0.2315	0.2392	0.2268	0.2338	0.2545	0.2527	
	2022	0.2112	0.2217	0.2109	0.2215	0.2143	0.2211	0.2089	0.2251	0.2225	0.2137	
CYCLE	2013	0.3178	0.3208	0.3214	0.3218	0.3241	0.3250	0.3219	0.3267	0.3235	0.3230	
	2014	0.2793	0.2793	0.2783	0.2776	0.2795	0.2798	0.2784	0.2835	0.2782	0.2816	
	2015	0.2956	0.2955	0.2960	0.2969	0.2989	0.2968	0.2969	0.3001	0.2943	0.2942	
	2016	0.3032	0.3027	0.3049	0.3053	0.3055	0.3060	0.3015	0.3071	0.3039	0.3053	
	2017	0.3083	0.3073	0.3102	0.3079	0.3102	0.3083	0.3084	0.3134	0.3084	0.3108	
	2018	0.2551	0.2533	0.2531	0.2527	0.2554	0.2534	0.2528	0.2560	0.2515	0.2532	
	2019	0.3089	0.3078	0.3101	0.3093	0.3107	0.3093	0.3182	0.3222	0.3186	0.3305	
	2020	0.2303	0.2296	0.2293	0.2311	0.2334	0.2321	0.2286	0.2350	0.2296	0.2302	
	2021	0.2910	0.2918	0.2895	0.2906	0.2915	0.2913	0.2895	0.2942	0.2950	0.2938	
	2022	0.2261	0.2260	0.2264	0.2258	0.2270	0.2253	0.2354	0.2372	0.2335	0.2348	

Table S3. Results between our model and the baseline models @4 ("Graph-TempEL: New entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.2955	0.2949	0.2971	0.2985	0.3002	0.2993	0.2975	0.3010	0.2964	0.2951	
	2014	0.2583	0.2598	0.2584	0.2591	0.2619	0.2610	0.2590	0.2613	0.2581	0.2608	
	2015	0.2846	0.2835	0.2857	0.2861	0.2885	0.2864	0.2849	0.2889	0.2843	0.2849	
	2016	0.2773	0.2777	0.2791	0.2781	0.2807	0.2791	0.2748	0.2788	0.2769	0.2781	
	2017	0.2906	0.2934	0.2944	0.2945	0.2977	0.2951	0.2927	0.2957	0.2924	0.2946	
	2018	0.2689	0.2677	0.2681	0.2685	0.2701	0.2700	0.2655	0.2707	0.2657	0.2689	
	2019	0.2914	0.2933	0.2933	0.2930	0.2948	0.2942	0.2928	0.2949	0.2915	0.2946	
	2020	0.2641	0.2630	0.2640	0.2656	0.2679	0.2660	0.2647	0.2679	0.2627	0.2648	
	2021	0.2689	0.2704	0.2699	0.2689	0.2714	0.2696	0.2666	0.2721	0.2739	0.2720	
	2022	0.2707	0.2709	0.2708	0.2715	0.2727	0.2708	0.2682	0.2743	0.2718	0.2733	
SpEL	2013	0.3553	0.3551	0.3471	0.3586	0.3701	0.3694	0.3673	0.3710	0.3561	0.3652	
	2014	0.3183	0.3099	0.3084	0.3291	0.3120	0.3310	0.3287	0.3312	0.3081	0.3209	
	2015	0.3547	0.3336	0.3356	0.3561	0.3382	0.3466	0.3448	0.3489	0.3340	0.3547	
	2016	0.3274	0.3278	0.3294	0.3282	0.3508	0.3495	0.3349	0.3288	0.3268	0.3284	
	2017	0.3608	0.3635	0.3443	0.3443	0.3576	0.3648	0.3424	0.3455	0.3419	0.3546	
	2018	0.3289	0.3276	0.3174	0.3182	0.3197	0.3200	0.3152	0.3303	0.3254	0.3385	
	2019	0.3412	0.3633	0.3630	0.3627	0.3646	0.3441	0.3626	0.3651	0.3414	0.3544	
	2020	0.3342	0.3333	0.3341	0.3254	0.3183	0.3261	0.3248	0.3280	0.3127	0.3249	
	2021	0.3386	0.3201	0.3299	0.3390	0.3415	0.3198	0.3263	0.3322	0.3239	0.3419	
	2022	0.3107	0.2906	0.2905	0.2918	0.2928	0.3112	0.3084	0.3041	0.3019	0.3031	
CYCLE	2013	0.4193	0.4189	0.4208	0.4230	0.4259	0.4252	0.4214	0.4251	0.4224	0.4251	
	2014	0.3762	0.3762	0.3780	0.3772	0.3811	0.3794	0.3753	0.3791	0.3771	0.3788	
	2015	0.3930	0.3941	0.3962	0.3966	0.3980	0.3968	0.3926	0.3962	0.3918	0.3930	
	2016	0.4030	0.4041	0.4072	0.4078	0.4092	0.4095	0.4042	0.4078	0.4047	0.4069	
	2017	0.4108	0.4125	0.4115	0.4120	0.4141	0.4130	0.4082	0.4157	0.4126	0.4132	
	2018	0.3506	0.3511	0.3499	0.3480	0.3522	0.3498	0.3479	0.3517	0.3487	0.3500	
	2019	0.4107	0.4116	0.4126	0.4125	0.4159	0.4218	0.4191	0.4244	0.4222	0.4341	
	2020	0.3483	0.3496	0.3510	0.3524	0.3573	0.3530	0.3500	0.3547	0.3489	0.3528	
	2021	0.3916	0.3924	0.3920	0.3927	0.3941	0.3928	0.3893	0.3960	0.3982	0.3945	
	2022	0.3326	0.3328	0.3335	0.3344	0.3337	0.3429	0.3493	0.3439	0.3405	0.3406	

Table S4. Results between our model and the baseline models @8 ("Graph-TempEL: New entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Train												
BLINK	2013	0.3889	0.3892	0.3914	0.3940	0.3939	0.3919	0.3911	0.3917	0.3879	0.3881	
	2014	0.3486	0.3489	0.3502	0.3497	0.3507	0.3497	0.3473	0.3492	0.3471	0.3489	
	2015	0.3755	0.3765	0.3792	0.3788	0.3815	0.3780	0.3746	0.3766	0.3749	0.3749	
	2016	0.3712	0.3691	0.3716	0.3715	0.3734	0.3719	0.3687	0.3722	0.3694	0.3704	
	2017	0.3861	0.3886	0.3899	0.3889	0.3917	0.3882	0.3864	0.3889	0.3872	0.3872	
	2018	0.3607	0.3599	0.3601	0.3591	0.3603	0.3590	0.3558	0.3605	0.3547	0.3576	
	2019	0.3861	0.3895	0.3892	0.3913	0.3906	0.3904	0.3876	0.3902	0.3884	0.3918	
	2020	0.3539	0.3559	0.3589	0.3591	0.3607	0.3573	0.3560	0.3602	0.3555	0.3585	
	2021	0.3605	0.3607	0.3618	0.3614	0.3643	0.3638	0.3585	0.3654	0.3691	0.3638	
	2022	0.3616	0.3632	0.3635	0.3642	0.3654	0.3628	0.3620	0.3655	0.3648	0.3645	
SpEL	2013	0.4488	0.4692	0.4613	0.4642	0.4637	0.4618	0.4610	0.4618	0.4581	0.4483	
	2014	0.4185	0.4289	0.4102	0.4199	0.4207	0.4094	0.4074	0.4292	0.4071	0.4293	
	2015	0.4554	0.4561	0.4592	0.4488	0.4619	0.4379	0.4545	0.4567	0.4447	0.4450	
	2016	0.4511	0.4493	0.4417	0.4415	0.4534	0.4316	0.4386	0.4420	0.4294	0.4404	
	2017	0.4562	0.4586	0.4700	0.4489	0.4617	0.4581	0.4662	0.4588	0.4472	0.4671	
	2018	0.4304	0.4296	0.4298	0.4387	0.4400	0.4388	0.4353	0.4200	0.4145	0.4373	
	2019	0.4460	0.4695	0.4592	0.4611	0.4706	0.4604	0.4475	0.4701	0.4585	0.4715	
	2020	0.4338	0.4158	0.4391	0.4389	0.4406	0.4373	0.4259	0.4203	0.4158	0.4185	
	2021	0.4304	0.4404	0.4320	0.4312	0.4244	0.4236	0.4184	0.4354	0.4288	0.4340	
	2022	0.3919	0.3931	0.4034	0.4142	0.4053	0.4028	0.4020	0.3955	0.3949	0.3946	
CYCLE	2013	0.5348	0.5376	0.5390	0.5423	0.5427	0.5434	0.5390	0.5418	0.5387	0.5400	
	2014	0.4960	0.4966	0.4989	0.4993	0.5007	0.4987	0.4967	0.4993	0.4965	0.4974	
	2015	0.5330	0.5334	0.5367	0.5363	0.5375	0.5363	0.5322	0.5354	0.5314	0.5318	
	2016	0.5273	0.5283	0.5318	0.5316	0.5328	0.5332	0.5299	0.5316	0.5298	0.5309	
	2017	0.5365	0.5375	0.5393	0.5380	0.5409	0.5371	0.5336	0.5383	0.5389	0.5421	
	2018	0.4590	0.4610	0.4605	0.4592	0.4626	0.4599	0.4563	0.4600	0.4568	0.4576	
	2019	0.5258	0.5262	0.5272	0.5284	0.5302	0.5382	0.5347	0.5372	0.5363	0.5481	
	2020	0.4423	0.4418	0.4459	0.4460	0.4493	0.4467	0.4449	0.4483	0.4441	0.4459	
	2021	0.5065	0.5071	0.5088	0.5082	0.5100	0.5074	0.5031	0.5064	0.5110	0.5092	
	2022	0.4416	0.4420	0.4433	0.4444	0.4449	0.4433	0.4595	0.4526	0.4518	0.4527	

Table S5. Results between our model and the baseline models @16 ("Graph-TempEL: New entities" as the training set).

		Test									
		2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Train											
	BLINK	2013	0.4861	0.4871	0.4895	0.4907	0.4933	0.4907	0.4877	0.4881	0.4849
2014		0.4454	0.4479	0.4478	0.4484	0.4490	0.4488	0.4470	0.4493	0.4448	0.4477
2015		0.4728	0.4758	0.4770	0.4782	0.4784	0.4765	0.4717	0.4723	0.4701	0.4711
2016		0.4708	0.4708	0.4736	0.4727	0.4748	0.4740	0.4701	0.4714	0.4691	0.4700
2017		0.4836	0.4868	0.4883	0.4885	0.4895	0.4897	0.4865	0.4876	0.4853	0.4855
2018		0.4560	0.4585	0.4588	0.4598	0.4590	0.4578	0.4549	0.4556	0.4515	0.4538
2019		0.4889	0.4922	0.4927	0.4931	0.4949	0.4935	0.4925	0.4920	0.4916	0.4910
2020		0.4563	0.4578	0.4607	0.4618	0.4627	0.4610	0.4579	0.4588	0.4554	0.4558
2021		0.4611	0.4610	0.4633	0.4627	0.4673	0.4652	0.4614	0.4631	0.4696	0.4650
2022		0.4601	0.4642	0.4642	0.4642	0.4670	0.4637	0.4634	0.4643	0.4631	0.4656
SpEL	2013	0.5661	0.5669	0.5597	0.5707	0.5733	0.5506	0.5578	0.5484	0.5446	0.5448
	2014	0.5252	0.5176	0.5077	0.5279	0.5194	0.5086	0.5069	0.5292	0.5249	0.5274
	2015	0.5428	0.5460	0.5568	0.5582	0.5585	0.5467	0.5415	0.5519	0.5299	0.5511
	2016	0.5308	0.5309	0.5437	0.5529	0.5547	0.5537	0.5502	0.5412	0.5490	0.5302
	2017	0.5434	0.5467	0.5486	0.5483	0.5593	0.5494	0.5664	0.5671	0.5549	0.5656
	2018	0.5359	0.5285	0.5289	0.5199	0.5384	0.5280	0.5248	0.5256	0.5113	0.5336
	2019	0.5684	0.5522	0.5728	0.5631	0.5547	0.5733	0.5621	0.5618	0.5713	0.5508
	2020	0.5261	0.5280	0.5308	0.5318	0.5425	0.5311	0.5282	0.5391	0.5257	0.5361
	2021	0.5411	0.5208	0.5333	0.5326	0.5371	0.5455	0.5213	0.5334	0.5396	0.5352
	2022	0.5100	0.5044	0.5141	0.5143	0.5071	0.5039	0.5135	0.5142	0.5030	0.5157
CYCLE	2013	0.6347	0.6371	0.6407	0.6385	0.6410	0.6399	0.6385	0.6381	0.6353	0.6377
	2014	0.5921	0.5932	0.5949	0.5968	0.5982	0.5985	0.5956	0.5963	0.5930	0.5955
	2015	0.6394	0.6408	0.6421	0.6435	0.6435	0.6431	0.6391	0.6396	0.6364	0.6380
	2016	0.6296	0.6322	0.6348	0.6330	0.6351	0.6331	0.6320	0.6338	0.6303	0.6327
	2017	0.6270	0.6320	0.6319	0.6324	0.6346	0.6312	0.6297	0.6299	0.6281	0.6310
	2018	0.5558	0.5581	0.5595	0.5588	0.5587	0.5568	0.5535	0.5544	0.5534	0.5536
	2019	0.6256	0.6310	0.6309	0.6302	0.6330	0.6323	0.6385	0.6395	0.6374	0.6443
	2020	0.5521	0.5547	0.5558	0.5583	0.5589	0.5572	0.5549	0.5570	0.5532	0.5543
	2021	0.6068	0.6093	0.6112	0.6106	0.6109	0.6090	0.6061	0.6079	0.6145	0.6126
	2022	0.5496	0.5515	0.5533	0.5556	0.5671	0.5519	0.5603	0.5622	0.5623	0.5614

Table S6. Results between our model and the baseline models @32 ("Graph-TempEL: New entities" as the training set).

		Test									
		2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Train											
BLINK	2013	0.5883	0.5907	0.5916	0.5905	0.5920	0.5898	0.5871	0.5872	0.5834	0.5854
	2014	0.5470	0.5505	0.5510	0.5503	0.5515	0.5510	0.5484	0.5491	0.5457	0.5475
	2015	0.5722	0.5769	0.5787	0.5775	0.5781	0.5770	0.5746	0.5737	0.5706	0.5709
	2016	0.5736	0.5772	0.5770	0.5759	0.5788	0.5759	0.5743	0.5736	0.5705	0.5712
	2017	0.5855	0.5897	0.5893	0.5873	0.5915	0.5900	0.5873	0.5872	0.5845	0.5864
	2018	0.5564	0.5591	0.5603	0.5588	0.5606	0.5600	0.5564	0.5567	0.5519	0.5540
	2019	0.5927	0.5962	0.5977	0.5945	0.5984	0.5961	0.5970	0.5941	0.5934	0.5930
	2020	0.5596	0.5625	0.5650	0.5637	0.5654	0.5648	0.5631	0.5639	0.5588	0.5605
	2021	0.5646	0.5659	0.5674	0.5684	0.5716	0.5707	0.5697	0.5700	0.5765	0.5738
	2022	0.5635	0.5680	0.5669	0.5680	0.5688	0.5678	0.5679	0.5679	0.5662	0.5665
SpEL	2013	0.6582	0.6507	0.6518	0.6607	0.6520	0.6499	0.6471	0.6570	0.6432	0.6555
	2014	0.6067	0.6205	0.6111	0.6107	0.6215	0.6309	0.6182	0.6091	0.6056	0.6271
	2015	0.6322	0.6566	0.6481	0.6373	0.6480	0.6572	0.6444	0.6438	0.6406	0.6409
	2016	0.6435	0.6571	0.6571	0.6360	0.6489	0.6361	0.6443	0.6538	0.6408	0.6515
	2017	0.6554	0.6594	0.6692	0.6673	0.6514	0.6700	0.6674	0.6473	0.6443	0.6460
	2018	0.6161	0.6188	0.6401	0.6287	0.6402	0.6298	0.6162	0.6263	0.6117	0.6136
	2019	0.6525	0.6760	0.6776	0.6543	0.6681	0.6561	0.6567	0.6540	0.6534	0.6730
	2020	0.6196	0.6227	0.6450	0.6340	0.6358	0.6247	0.6331	0.6342	0.6388	0.6206
	2021	0.6444	0.6457	0.6275	0.6284	0.6416	0.6507	0.6496	0.6399	0.6565	0.6438
	2022	0.6234	0.6179	0.6168	0.6177	0.6285	0.6279	0.6181	0.6277	0.6264	0.6160
CYCLE	2013	0.7343	0.7340	0.7367	0.7351	0.7370	0.7354	0.7327	0.7334	0.7303	0.7326
	2014	0.6931	0.6947	0.6974	0.6968	0.6986	0.6984	0.6960	0.6947	0.6923	0.6948
	2015	0.7201	0.7232	0.7254	0.7251	0.7249	0.7243	0.7228	0.7204	0.7187	0.7207
	2016	0.7159	0.7166	0.7198	0.7175	0.7213	0.7176	0.7154	0.7145	0.7130	0.7153
	2017	0.7223	0.7249	0.7274	0.7241	0.7269	0.7243	0.7259	0.7242	0.7227	0.7228
	2018	0.6559	0.6593	0.6613	0.6609	0.6627	0.6606	0.6578	0.6585	0.6554	0.6557
	2019	0.7218	0.7237	0.7259	0.7241	0.7275	0.7242	0.7234	0.7213	0.7194	0.7306
	2020	0.6572	0.6607	0.6589	0.6605	0.6620	0.6605	0.6593	0.6587	0.6551	0.6563
	2021	0.7087	0.7124	0.7137	0.7127	0.7145	0.7125	0.7107	0.7123	0.7171	0.7143
	2022	0.6539	0.6562	0.6569	0.6576	0.6584	0.6576	0.6564	0.6561	0.6554	0.6574

Table S7. Results between our model and the baseline models @64 ("Graph-TempEL: New entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.6829	0.6858	0.6879	0.6850	0.6861	0.6867	0.6838	0.6834	0.6808	0.6833	
	2014	0.6497	0.6526	0.6518	0.6507	0.6523	0.6523	0.6498	0.6505	0.6474	0.6495	
	2015	0.6718	0.6747	0.6764	0.6747	0.6740	0.6728	0.6722	0.6706	0.6698	0.6705	
	2016	0.6746	0.6770	0.6778	0.6763	0.6782	0.6750	0.6748	0.6759	0.6742	0.6750	
	2017	0.6845	0.6868	0.6874	0.6852	0.6878	0.6878	0.6843	0.6852	0.6843	0.6859	
	2018	0.6581	0.6608	0.6621	0.6576	0.6601	0.6597	0.6583	0.6572	0.6559	0.6566	
	2019	0.6936	0.6955	0.6954	0.6948	0.6968	0.6954	0.6946	0.6920	0.6934	0.6943	
	2020	0.6641	0.6671	0.6676	0.6662	0.6674	0.6662	0.6658	0.6655	0.6631	0.6651	
	2021	0.6679	0.6705	0.6711	0.6708	0.6739	0.6731	0.6726	0.6712	0.6762	0.6735	
	2022	0.6640	0.6677	0.6689	0.6676	0.6707	0.6708	0.6691	0.6686	0.6708	0.6701	
SpEL	2013	0.7531	0.7558	0.7479	0.7350	0.7361	0.7367	0.7440	0.7334	0.7309	0.7432	
	2014	0.7199	0.7226	0.7216	0.7208	0.7223	0.7024	0.7195	0.7104	0.7071	0.7092	
	2015	0.7218	0.7347	0.7261	0.7346	0.7238	0.7429	0.7221	0.7305	0.7296	0.7405	
	2016	0.7445	0.7474	0.7375	0.7463	0.7484	0.7252	0.7447	0.7259	0.7443	0.7451	
	2017	0.7345	0.7567	0.7573	0.7450	0.7476	0.7376	0.7443	0.7549	0.7542	0.7459	
	2018	0.7083	0.7303	0.7117	0.7174	0.7100	0.7095	0.7182	0.7071	0.7054	0.7265	
	2019	0.7634	0.7554	0.7654	0.7549	0.7467	0.7553	0.7645	0.7621	0.7634	0.7539	
	2020	0.7242	0.7172	0.7376	0.7262	0.7176	0.7163	0.7258	0.7254	0.7132	0.7154	
	2021	0.7381	0.7402	0.7211	0.7208	0.7238	0.7430	0.7326	0.7313	0.7362	0.7236	
	2022	0.6939	0.6977	0.7090	0.7177	0.7205	0.7209	0.6991	0.7183	0.7007	0.6999	
CYCLE	2013	0.8129	0.8132	0.8142	0.8129	0.8156	0.8129	0.8108	0.8109	0.8109	0.8124	
	2014	0.7628	0.7670	0.7654	0.7636	0.7661	0.7653	0.7632	0.7619	0.7590	0.7612	
	2015	0.8110	0.8154	0.8164	0.8137	0.8142	0.8136	0.8135	0.8120	0.8089	0.8108	
	2016	0.8075	0.8086	0.8093	0.8071	0.8089	0.8081	0.8058	0.8063	0.8059	0.8067	
	2017	0.7912	0.7945	0.7955	0.7931	0.7959	0.7949	0.7940	0.7938	0.7937	0.7950	
	2018	0.7578	0.7610	0.7613	0.7588	0.7609	0.7592	0.7578	0.7581	0.7561	0.7575	
	2019	0.8005	0.8029	0.8054	0.8019	0.8040	0.8027	0.8009	0.8000	0.7991	0.8106	
	2020	0.7585	0.7613	0.7624	0.7624	0.7631	0.7615	0.7602	0.7586	0.7581	0.7577	
	2021	0.7890	0.7914	0.7931	0.7915	0.7949	0.7913	0.7915	0.7923	0.7975	0.7932	
	2022	0.7588	0.7615	0.7610	0.7591	0.7616	0.7615	0.7597	0.7598	0.7594	0.7617	

2. ADDITIONAL RESULTS - CONTINUAL ENTITIES TRAINING SET

Tables S8 through Table S14 present a comparison between the baseline models (BLINK and SpEL) and our model CYCLE. The dataset, "Graph-TempEL: Continual entities," has a training set (1,764), a validation set ($\approx 42k$, same as original TempEL dataset), and a test set ($\approx 48k$, same as original TempEL dataset). Here, the training set contains only 1,764 samples because, in the original TempEL dataset, each year's dataset contains only 1,764 'new entities' samples. For comparison, we also have 1,764 'continual entity' samples. Rows represent training datasets, while columns represent testing datasets. Performance evaluations for all models were based on recall metrics, specifically @1, @2, @4, @8, @16, @32, and @64.

Table S8. Results between our model and the baseline models @1 ("Graph-TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set).

		Test									
		2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Train											
	BLINK	2013	0.1710	0.1719	0.1712	0.1727	0.1719	0.1736	0.1701	0.1761	0.1743
2014		0.1585	0.1593	0.1598	0.1613	0.1608	0.1587	0.1584	0.1625	0.1621	0.1620
2015		0.1854	0.1870	0.1878	0.1879	0.1897	0.1887	0.1855	0.1913	0.1898	0.1909
2016		0.1581	0.1589	0.1579	0.1595	0.1609	0.1602	0.1575	0.1614	0.1597	0.1589
2017		0.1926	0.1953	0.1950	0.1947	0.1961	0.1944	0.1901	0.1984	0.1952	0.1944
2018		0.1797	0.1782	0.1779	0.1786	0.1774	0.1799	0.1760	0.1833	0.1817	0.1801
2019		0.1757	0.1767	0.1766	0.1763	0.1775	0.1775	0.1729	0.1785	0.1783	0.1774
2020		0.1841	0.1867	0.1873	0.1869	0.1890	0.1874	0.1843	0.1901	0.1875	0.1866
2021		0.1759	0.1752	0.1742	0.1760	0.1769	0.1754	0.1735	0.1797	0.1771	0.1758
2022		0.1623	0.1641	0.1645	0.1666	0.1673	0.1656	0.1634	0.1686	0.1665	0.1665
SpEL	2013	0.2275	0.2133	0.2269	0.2133	0.2296	0.2237	0.2130	0.2284	0.2153	0.2264
	2014	0.2039	0.2160	0.2065	0.2179	0.2095	0.2091	0.2041	0.2191	0.2078	0.2213
	2015	0.2409	0.2430	0.2337	0.2331	0.2356	0.2301	0.2298	0.2373	0.2493	0.2430
	2016	0.1983	0.2124	0.2165	0.2188	0.2151	0.2044	0.2011	0.2197	0.2173	0.2166
	2017	0.2446	0.2447	0.2418	0.2347	0.2516	0.2346	0.2317	0.2421	0.2414	0.2391
	2018	0.2205	0.2342	0.2353	0.2291	0.2281	0.2271	0.2358	0.2243	0.2335	0.2342
	2019	0.2268	0.2356	0.2246	0.2285	0.2305	0.2278	0.2234	0.2275	0.2253	0.2209
	2020	0.2362	0.2426	0.2341	0.2348	0.2473	0.2391	0.2309	0.2496	0.2457	0.2314
	2021	0.2302	0.2251	0.2185	0.2218	0.2170	0.2312	0.2190	0.2315	0.2217	0.2279
	2022	0.2199	0.2187	0.2088	0.2223	0.2126	0.2240	0.2201	0.2191	0.2234	0.2193
CYCLE	2013	0.2533	0.2529	0.2524	0.2550	0.2536	0.2528	0.2492	0.2552	0.2543	0.2537
	2014	0.2612	0.2614	0.2604	0.2630	0.2626	0.2616	0.2591	0.2644	0.2629	0.2637
	2015	0.2773	0.2759	0.2767	0.2759	0.2761	0.2751	0.2720	0.2783	0.2776	0.2777
	2016	0.2866	0.2849	0.2855	0.2865	0.2876	0.2866	0.2836	0.2886	0.2864	0.2870
	2017	0.3153	0.3167	0.3185	0.3184	0.3209	0.3179	0.3156	0.3219	0.3182	0.3177
	2018	0.2910	0.2901	0.2892	0.2911	0.2907	0.2900	0.2875	0.2931	0.2905	0.2899
	2019	0.2971	0.2978	0.2990	0.2997	0.3010	0.2997	0.2960	0.3015	0.2999	0.3010
	2020	0.2852	0.2834	0.2838	0.2838	0.2847	0.2839	0.2912	0.2954	0.2925	0.2949
	2021	0.2728	0.2728	0.2721	0.2725	0.2755	0.2747	0.2704	0.2765	0.2745	0.2738
	2022	0.2762	0.2756	0.2759	0.2761	0.2771	0.2759	0.2728	0.2776	0.2770	0.2777

Table S9. Results between our model and the baseline models @2 ("Graph-TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.2534	0.2539	0.2531	0.2556	0.2549	0.2540	0.2514	0.2575	0.2566	0.2551	
	2014	0.2363	0.2358	0.2381	0.2384	0.2400	0.2381	0.2349	0.2389	0.2400	0.2397	
	2015	0.2689	0.2736	0.2726	0.2742	0.2760	0.2739	0.2710	0.2775	0.2771	0.2750	
	2016	0.2332	0.2373	0.2357	0.2364	0.2386	0.2375	0.2325	0.2387	0.2375	0.2361	
	2017	0.2804	0.2809	0.2831	0.2816	0.2850	0.2824	0.2805	0.2871	0.2858	0.2846	
	2018	0.2605	0.2610	0.2613	0.2613	0.2625	0.2640	0.2581	0.2643	0.2651	0.2649	
	2019	0.2605	0.2592	0.2612	0.2583	0.2624	0.2593	0.2565	0.2626	0.2633	0.2630	
	2020	0.2701	0.2716	0.2727	0.2726	0.2743	0.2733	0.2673	0.2739	0.2722	0.2730	
	2021	0.2581	0.2586	0.2596	0.2581	0.2612	0.2595	0.2550	0.2608	0.2624	0.2598	
	2022	0.2423	0.2430	0.2441	0.2443	0.2474	0.2453	0.2422	0.2480	0.2481	0.2456	
SpEL	2013	0.3104	0.3087	0.3132	0.3079	0.3209	0.3072	0.3185	0.3095	0.3196	0.3124	
	2014	0.3011	0.2988	0.3049	0.3010	0.3093	0.2942	0.2940	0.3030	0.3000	0.3092	
	2015	0.3351	0.3357	0.3244	0.3274	0.3271	0.3306	0.3245	0.3379	0.3283	0.3390	
	2016	0.2859	0.3067	0.2954	0.2968	0.2962	0.2891	0.2907	0.2988	0.3056	0.2975	
	2017	0.3393	0.3447	0.3508	0.3501	0.3545	0.3354	0.3348	0.3483	0.3462	0.3481	
	2018	0.3151	0.3150	0.3154	0.3250	0.3212	0.3218	0.3094	0.3315	0.3268	0.3310	
	2019	0.3107	0.3273	0.3219	0.3168	0.3134	0.3108	0.3142	0.3305	0.3247	0.3221	
	2020	0.3225	0.3389	0.3231	0.3324	0.3361	0.3334	0.3231	0.3403	0.3332	0.3297	
	2021	0.3137	0.3171	0.3181	0.3168	0.3145	0.3261	0.3076	0.3225	0.3245	0.3204	
	2022	0.3063	0.2943	0.3025	0.3079	0.3145	0.3075	0.2989	0.3157	0.3162	0.3006	
CYCLE	2013	0.3680	0.3668	0.3682	0.3716	0.3710	0.3685	0.3657	0.3706	0.3705	0.3688	
	2014	0.3698	0.3691	0.3700	0.3716	0.3735	0.3722	0.3685	0.3737	0.3735	0.3735	
	2015	0.3702	0.3708	0.3719	0.3710	0.3730	0.3714	0.3673	0.3739	0.3748	0.3723	
	2016	0.4086	0.4093	0.4086	0.4087	0.4114	0.4090	0.4051	0.4109	0.4114	0.4085	
	2017	0.4127	0.4157	0.4183	0.4159	0.4199	0.4172	0.4137	0.4208	0.4198	0.4175	
	2018	0.4149	0.4121	0.4126	0.4138	0.4161	0.4139	0.4101	0.4165	0.4162	0.4138	
	2019	0.4070	0.4095	0.4100	0.4121	0.4129	0.4113	0.4059	0.4129	0.4118	0.4133	
	2020	0.4058	0.4048	0.4043	0.4049	0.4056	0.4035	0.4110	0.4188	0.4145	0.4145	
	2021	0.3982	0.3991	0.3991	0.3990	0.4016	0.3999	0.3951	0.4025	0.4022	0.4001	
	2022	0.3842	0.3841	0.3841	0.3860	0.3878	0.3858	0.3816	0.3878	0.3869	0.3868	

Table S10. Results between our model and the baseline models @4 ("Graph-TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set).

		Test										
		2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	
Train												
	BLINK	2013	0.3479	0.3500	0.3494	0.3500	0.3549	0.3510	0.3469	0.3536	0.3554	0.3522
2014		0.3260	0.3289	0.3301	0.3305	0.3341	0.3302	0.3264	0.3337	0.3355	0.3327	
2015		0.3651	0.3680	0.3693	0.3721	0.3722	0.3691	0.3673	0.3712	0.3749	0.3716	
2016		0.3262	0.3266	0.3260	0.3277	0.3308	0.3287	0.3220	0.3287	0.3316	0.3280	
2017		0.3800	0.3813	0.3832	0.3836	0.3861	0.3835	0.3799	0.3854	0.3861	0.3830	
2018		0.3576	0.3570	0.3569	0.3585	0.3603	0.3600	0.3540	0.3596	0.3637	0.3593	
2019		0.3570	0.3567	0.3596	0.3567	0.3619	0.3582	0.3546	0.3604	0.3625	0.3624	
2020		0.3668	0.3697	0.3713	0.3729	0.3738	0.3716	0.3657	0.3722	0.3730	0.3724	
2021		0.3540	0.3567	0.3538	0.3549	0.3609	0.3565	0.3519	0.3575	0.3599	0.3575	
2022		0.3352	0.3362	0.3382	0.3374	0.3410	0.3391	0.3368	0.3418	0.3423	0.3410	
SpEL	2013	0.4081	0.4103	0.4155	0.4107	0.4328	0.4125	0.4111	0.4206	0.4169	0.4320	
	2014	0.3903	0.3985	0.3950	0.4009	0.4118	0.4048	0.4038	0.3974	0.4065	0.3960	
	2015	0.4395	0.4365	0.4351	0.4401	0.4473	0.4354	0.4365	0.4450	0.4357	0.4335	
	2016	0.3889	0.3933	0.4010	0.3998	0.4024	0.4024	0.4002	0.3932	0.3995	0.3880	
	2017	0.4458	0.4593	0.4531	0.4577	0.4601	0.4485	0.4505	0.4622	0.4519	0.4462	
	2018	0.4341	0.4215	0.4361	0.4352	0.4353	0.4210	0.4330	0.4267	0.4292	0.4361	
	2019	0.4274	0.4309	0.4353	0.4343	0.4387	0.4211	0.4215	0.4360	0.4268	0.4294	
	2020	0.4431	0.4424	0.4447	0.4348	0.4481	0.4413	0.4370	0.4437	0.4471	0.4332	
	2021	0.4297	0.4172	0.4196	0.4165	0.4373	0.4262	0.4137	0.4367	0.4350	0.4237	
	2022	0.4065	0.4143	0.3991	0.4023	0.4109	0.4126	0.4133	0.4084	0.4107	0.4155	
CYCLE	2013	0.4637	0.4649	0.4675	0.4675	0.4697	0.4670	0.4631	0.4681	0.4710	0.4691	
	2014	0.4833	0.4855	0.4851	0.4877	0.4914	0.4880	0.4832	0.4896	0.4883	0.4861	
	2015	0.4966	0.4987	0.4995	0.4990	0.5025	0.4992	0.4951	0.5006	0.5029	0.4993	
	2016	0.5230	0.5261	0.5253	0.5273	0.5292	0.5262	0.5207	0.5267	0.5283	0.5257	
	2017	0.5338	0.5365	0.5377	0.5388	0.5411	0.5385	0.5363	0.5409	0.5416	0.5380	
	2018	0.5292	0.5303	0.5304	0.5314	0.5353	0.5324	0.5288	0.5330	0.5354	0.5322	
	2019	0.5374	0.5406	0.5408	0.5418	0.5435	0.5419	0.5370	0.5429	0.5443	0.5434	
	2020	0.5083	0.5091	0.5101	0.5086	0.5109	0.5078	0.5249	0.5297	0.5301	0.5198	
	2021	0.5042	0.5062	0.5066	0.5066	0.5112	0.5074	0.5042	0.5084	0.5123	0.5094	
	2022	0.5053	0.5086	0.5084	0.5093	0.5117	0.5091	0.5052	0.5097	0.5106	0.5081	

Table S11. Results between our model and the baseline models @8 ("Graph-TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.4531	0.4544	0.4538	0.4565	0.4586	0.4550	0.4531	0.4574	0.4609	0.4564	
	2014	0.4314	0.4327	0.4322	0.4347	0.4385	0.4338	0.4314	0.4360	0.4409	0.4393	
	2015	0.4700	0.4721	0.4723	0.4749	0.4774	0.4749	0.4714	0.4745	0.4776	0.4761	
	2016	0.4258	0.4285	0.4296	0.4306	0.4354	0.4316	0.4260	0.4296	0.4363	0.4317	
	2017	0.4863	0.4887	0.4880	0.4906	0.4918	0.4902	0.4886	0.4898	0.4931	0.4905	
	2018	0.4616	0.4638	0.4600	0.4639	0.4656	0.4624	0.4604	0.4620	0.4657	0.4642	
	2019	0.4614	0.4663	0.4668	0.4658	0.4689	0.4670	0.4627	0.4650	0.4698	0.4695	
	2020	0.4719	0.4753	0.4762	0.4772	0.4790	0.4766	0.4730	0.4776	0.4785	0.4795	
	2021	0.4551	0.4591	0.4594	0.4602	0.4640	0.4611	0.4586	0.4609	0.4651	0.4640	
	2022	0.4396	0.4421	0.4409	0.4433	0.4454	0.4428	0.4391	0.4442	0.4473	0.4455	
SpEL	2013	0.5321	0.5425	0.5336	0.5353	0.5355	0.5303	0.5268	0.5385	0.5376	0.5383	
	2014	0.5158	0.5082	0.5131	0.5224	0.5201	0.5120	0.5027	0.5133	0.5236	0.5185	
	2015	0.5572	0.5510	0.5449	0.5557	0.5642	0.5459	0.5607	0.5482	0.5627	0.5588	
	2016	0.5118	0.5015	0.5160	0.5091	0.5144	0.5134	0.5124	0.4999	0.5228	0.5168	
	2017	0.5704	0.5785	0.5739	0.5770	0.5805	0.5718	0.5753	0.5598	0.5661	0.5720	
	2018	0.5337	0.5441	0.5473	0.5364	0.5554	0.5361	0.5482	0.5411	0.5387	0.5428	
	2019	0.5331	0.5535	0.5431	0.5415	0.5478	0.5497	0.5485	0.5466	0.5470	0.5481	
	2020	0.5589	0.5637	0.5597	0.5614	0.5648	0.5559	0.5433	0.5519	0.5523	0.5617	
	2021	0.5252	0.5304	0.5374	0.5456	0.5390	0.5418	0.5325	0.5314	0.5522	0.5344	
	2022	0.5105	0.5245	0.5150	0.5320	0.5258	0.5162	0.5221	0.5164	0.5350	0.5308	
CYCLE	2013	0.5878	0.5898	0.5926	0.5922	0.5958	0.5923	0.5904	0.5919	0.5960	0.5942	
	2014	0.5873	0.5898	0.5913	0.5916	0.5947	0.5917	0.5881	0.5924	0.5949	0.5940	
	2015	0.6086	0.6120	0.6132	0.6139	0.6166	0.6131	0.6101	0.6118	0.6177	0.6137	
	2016	0.6282	0.6303	0.6293	0.6309	0.6347	0.6310	0.6279	0.6311	0.6352	0.6305	
	2017	0.6499	0.6526	0.6536	0.6559	0.6567	0.6552	0.6528	0.6553	0.6571	0.6557	
	2018	0.6131	0.6153	0.6150	0.6177	0.6210	0.6158	0.6152	0.6152	0.6198	0.6190	
	2019	0.6421	0.6461	0.6477	0.6474	0.6490	0.6483	0.6455	0.6485	0.6499	0.6484	
	2020	0.6205	0.6222	0.6226	0.6228	0.6262	0.6244	0.6497	0.6421	0.6462	0.6447	
	2021	0.6166	0.6209	0.6212	0.6213	0.6258	0.6221	0.6204	0.6228	0.6266	0.6261	
	2022	0.6101	0.6136	0.6149	0.6151	0.6171	0.6143	0.6112	0.6137	0.6174	0.6173	

Table S12. Results between our model and the baseline models @16 ("Graph-TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.5589	0.5606	0.5615	0.5625	0.5653	0.5625	0.5614	0.5622	0.5683	0.5640	
	2014	0.5393	0.5424	0.5436	0.5450	0.5473	0.5416	0.5414	0.5443	0.5490	0.5457	
	2015	0.5774	0.5790	0.5787	0.5801	0.5813	0.5820	0.5821	0.5814	0.5838	0.5829	
	2016	0.5339	0.5377	0.5375	0.5372	0.5430	0.5396	0.5381	0.5367	0.5412	0.5389	
	2017	0.5901	0.5945	0.5952	0.5970	0.5985	0.5970	0.5966	0.5966	0.5986	0.5970	
	2018	0.5677	0.5707	0.5691	0.5710	0.5725	0.5695	0.5680	0.5700	0.5736	0.5705	
	2019	0.5715	0.5742	0.5744	0.5752	0.5772	0.5737	0.5726	0.5740	0.5774	0.5782	
	2020	0.5779	0.5806	0.5835	0.5842	0.5856	0.5817	0.5819	0.5839	0.5840	0.5849	
	2021	0.5631	0.5665	0.5662	0.5682	0.5728	0.5684	0.5667	0.5680	0.5718	0.5695	
	2022	0.5465	0.5499	0.5498	0.5514	0.5524	0.5479	0.5469	0.5498	0.5529	0.5541	
SpEL	2013	0.6296	0.6228	0.6277	0.6404	0.6316	0.6352	0.6397	0.6279	0.6365	0.6422	
	2014	0.6073	0.6098	0.6121	0.6203	0.6121	0.6203	0.6033	0.6203	0.6277	0.6063	
	2015	0.6480	0.6492	0.6482	0.6405	0.6443	0.6454	0.6429	0.6609	0.6579	0.6518	
	2016	0.5947	0.6009	0.5981	0.6037	0.6130	0.6174	0.5982	0.6100	0.6082	0.6008	
	2017	0.6690	0.6680	0.6662	0.6626	0.6731	0.6720	0.6645	0.6729	0.6620	0.6600	
	2018	0.6462	0.6472	0.6292	0.6368	0.6415	0.6393	0.6377	0.6495	0.6531	0.6395	
	2019	0.6370	0.6438	0.6362	0.6397	0.6407	0.6443	0.6516	0.6406	0.6494	0.6516	
	2020	0.6539	0.6515	0.6518	0.6566	0.6529	0.6423	0.6565	0.6622	0.6599	0.6627	
	2021	0.6354	0.6291	0.6351	0.6413	0.6341	0.6355	0.6310	0.6330	0.6371	0.6336	
	2022	0.6191	0.6215	0.6271	0.6283	0.6156	0.6164	0.6094	0.6146	0.6266	0.6277	
CYCLE	2013	0.6948	0.6955	0.6968	0.6972	0.7017	0.6983	0.6976	0.6981	0.7015	0.6980	
	2014	0.6954	0.7001	0.7003	0.7016	0.7039	0.7001	0.7002	0.7009	0.7033	0.7004	
	2015	0.7062	0.7097	0.7083	0.7089	0.7109	0.7080	0.7070	0.7075	0.7113	0.7097	
	2016	0.7336	0.7357	0.7368	0.7370	0.7420	0.7369	0.7363	0.7357	0.7399	0.7380	
	2017	0.7258	0.7278	0.7311	0.7306	0.7339	0.7316	0.7308	0.7320	0.7333	0.7313	
	2018	0.7191	0.7231	0.7219	0.7238	0.7268	0.7256	0.7241	0.7234	0.7291	0.7274	
	2019	0.7078	0.7096	0.7115	0.7125	0.7118	0.7111	0.7088	0.7101	0.7132	0.7152	
	2020	0.7091	0.7118	0.7122	0.7119	0.7155	0.7128	0.7318	0.7301	0.7341	0.7342	
	2021	0.7067	0.7082	0.7103	0.7123	0.7136	0.7120	0.7104	0.7111	0.7136	0.7130	
	2022	0.7188	0.7219	0.7214	0.7234	0.7257	0.7226	0.7218	0.7225	0.7244	0.7248	

Table S13. Results between our model and the baseline models @32 ("Graph-TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.6631	0.6651	0.6671	0.6682	0.6688	0.6688	0.6648	0.6659	0.6687	0.6684	
	2014	0.6459	0.6524	0.6515	0.6515	0.6548	0.6508	0.6492	0.6531	0.6553	0.6542	
	2015	0.6797	0.6825	0.6840	0.6839	0.6849	0.6837	0.6837	0.6830	0.6851	0.6849	
	2016	0.6425	0.6452	0.6438	0.6447	0.6471	0.6443	0.6442	0.6435	0.6463	0.6465	
	2017	0.6912	0.6955	0.6975	0.6987	0.6994	0.6982	0.6986	0.6986	0.6993	0.6982	
	2018	0.6693	0.6737	0.6720	0.6731	0.6752	0.6724	0.6710	0.6708	0.6749	0.6735	
	2019	0.6743	0.6789	0.6807	0.6805	0.6815	0.6782	0.6795	0.6797	0.6820	0.6826	
	2020	0.6813	0.6829	0.6849	0.6855	0.6878	0.6858	0.6849	0.6860	0.6862	0.6884	
	2021	0.6658	0.6703	0.6698	0.6703	0.6734	0.6716	0.6697	0.6718	0.6745	0.6734	
	2022	0.6536	0.6560	0.6570	0.6568	0.6600	0.6565	0.6565	0.6590	0.6604	0.6607	
SpEL	2013	0.7148	0.7248	0.7236	0.7270	0.7261	0.7289	0.7243	0.7341	0.7297	0.7208	
	2014	0.6996	0.7158	0.7155	0.7027	0.7214	0.7140	0.6999	0.7036	0.7099	0.7120	
	2015	0.7368	0.7446	0.7458	0.7411	0.7386	0.7526	0.7407	0.7389	0.7507	0.7480	
	2016	0.6936	0.7022	0.7054	0.7133	0.7033	0.7053	0.7124	0.7107	0.6975	0.7066	
	2017	0.7476	0.7583	0.7606	0.7633	0.7533	0.7541	0.7610	0.7547	0.7679	0.7502	
	2018	0.7233	0.7296	0.7247	0.7251	0.7279	0.7381	0.7298	0.7248	0.7370	0.7392	
	2019	0.7251	0.7358	0.7317	0.7326	0.7473	0.7425	0.7371	0.7399	0.7370	0.7407	
	2020	0.7404	0.7517	0.7484	0.7371	0.7494	0.7548	0.7408	0.7476	0.7531	0.7506	
	2021	0.7315	0.7322	0.7204	0.7231	0.7241	0.7253	0.7241	0.7407	0.7284	0.7246	
	2022	0.7202	0.7215	0.7148	0.7132	0.7189	0.7104	0.7106	0.7092	0.7253	0.7137	
CYCLE	2013	0.7858	0.7887	0.7892	0.7890	0.7927	0.7894	0.7878	0.7894	0.7923	0.7905	
	2014	0.7734	0.7791	0.7773	0.7773	0.7795	0.7750	0.7752	0.7774	0.7783	0.7769	
	2015	0.7984	0.8017	0.8020	0.8013	0.8042	0.8012	0.8001	0.8016	0.8042	0.8038	
	2016	0.8185	0.8218	0.8225	0.8226	0.8252	0.8230	0.8225	0.8209	0.8232	0.8233	
	2017	0.8153	0.8209	0.8218	0.8213	0.8233	0.8221	0.8199	0.8221	0.8220	0.8208	
	2018	0.8055	0.8077	0.8074	0.8093	0.8111	0.8092	0.8075	0.8072	0.8100	0.8100	
	2019	0.8059	0.8084	0.8106	0.8114	0.8126	0.8105	0.8084	0.8098	0.8126	0.8121	
	2020	0.8047	0.8080	0.8095	0.8101	0.8115	0.8091	0.8278	0.8293	0.8205	0.8210	
	2021	0.7995	0.8033	0.8037	0.8050	0.8064	0.8067	0.8042	0.8050	0.8061	0.8070	
	2022	0.7955	0.8002	0.8001	0.8003	0.8040	0.8002	0.7989	0.8013	0.8028	0.8021	

Table S14. Results between our model and the baseline models @64 ("Graph-TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.7594	0.7617	0.7625	0.7613	0.7628	0.7621	0.7614	0.7628	0.7651	0.7639	
	2014	0.7489	0.7538	0.7532	0.7537	0.7546	0.7529	0.7517	0.7541	0.7551	0.7539	
	2015	0.7731	0.7758	0.7768	0.7776	0.7766	0.7754	0.7749	0.7746	0.7780	0.7769	
	2016	0.7421	0.7449	0.7419	0.7456	0.7441	0.7434	0.7425	0.7413	0.7441	0.7440	
	2017	0.7840	0.7880	0.7890	0.7886	0.7880	0.7873	0.7864	0.7867	0.7899	0.7873	
	2018	0.7650	0.7669	0.7660	0.7660	0.7668	0.7649	0.7641	0.7657	0.7688	0.7666	
	2019	0.7695	0.7745	0.7759	0.7758	0.7764	0.7752	0.7749	0.7750	0.7770	0.7755	
	2020	0.7742	0.7764	0.7765	0.7763	0.7788	0.7760	0.7767	0.7779	0.7788	0.7793	
	2021	0.7621	0.7655	0.7659	0.7659	0.7669	0.7660	0.7640	0.7651	0.7675	0.7667	
	2022	0.7506	0.7565	0.7560	0.7550	0.7588	0.7550	0.7556	0.7562	0.7583	0.7575	
SpEL	2013	0.8156	0.8058	0.8220	0.8155	0.8169	0.8190	0.8204	0.8169	0.8144	0.8096	
	2014	0.7936	0.8021	0.8042	0.8071	0.8033	0.8041	0.8011	0.7942	0.8085	0.8102	
	2015	0.8169	0.8340	0.8209	0.8244	0.8253	0.8170	0.8341	0.8257	0.8338	0.8243	
	2016	0.7976	0.7905	0.7877	0.7877	0.8029	0.7973	0.7997	0.7969	0.7891	0.7875	
	2017	0.8438	0.8436	0.8469	0.8424	0.8422	0.8405	0.8463	0.8311	0.8405	0.8427	
	2018	0.8223	0.8249	0.8197	0.8173	0.8131	0.8220	0.8046	0.8091	0.8136	0.8186	
	2019	0.8173	0.8266	0.8273	0.8228	0.8275	0.8227	0.8322	0.8344	0.8310	0.8241	
	2020	0.8172	0.8313	0.8325	0.8222	0.8337	0.8258	0.8237	0.8197	0.8381	0.8195	
	2021	0.8099	0.8073	0.8132	0.8251	0.8130	0.8109	0.8213	0.8128	0.8117	0.8082	
	2022	0.8000	0.8153	0.7979	0.8052	0.8024	0.8027	0.8145	0.8108	0.8160	0.8148	
CYCLE	2013	0.8481	0.8512	0.8525	0.8508	0.8536	0.8518	0.8497	0.8518	0.8537	0.8544	
	2014	0.8536	0.8579	0.8590	0.8561	0.8573	0.8546	0.8538	0.8563	0.8579	0.8562	
	2015	0.8522	0.8553	0.8559	0.8546	0.8546	0.8531	0.8533	0.8529	0.8544	0.8546	
	2016	0.8650	0.8686	0.8677	0.8677	0.8683	0.8662	0.8650	0.8658	0.8673	0.8667	
	2017	0.8773	0.8803	0.8817	0.8816	0.8820	0.8803	0.8793	0.8802	0.8808	0.8812	
	2018	0.8698	0.8732	0.8711	0.8721	0.8740	0.8725	0.8718	0.8721	0.8744	0.8738	
	2019	0.8737	0.8747	0.8756	0.8759	0.8772	0.8765	0.8762	0.8757	0.8788	0.8776	
	2020	0.8617	0.8660	0.8668	0.8682	0.8689	0.8664	0.8692	0.8683	0.8696	0.8697	
	2021	0.8637	0.8672	0.8674	0.8686	0.8682	0.8695	0.8678	0.8689	0.8700	0.8698	
	2022	0.8663	0.8689	0.8688	0.8684	0.8702	0.8691	0.8696	0.8694	0.8718	0.8705	

3. ADDITIONAL RESULTS - MITIGATING TEMPORAL DEGRADATION

Table S15 to Table S18 illuminate the effectiveness of our model in mitigating temporal degradation using results derived from the Graph-TempEL dataset. In Table S15 and Table S16, we use "Graph-TempEL: New entities" as the training set. In Table S17 and Table S18, we use "Graph-TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set. Each column in the table represents the years' gap between the training and testing datasets, as denoted by the digits from 0 to 9. For instance, 0 implies that training and testing datasets come from the same year, while 9 indicates that the model was trained in 2013 and tested in 2022. The rows are divided based on various metrics, includes @1, @2, @4, @8, @16, @32 and @64. "Boost" displays a comparison between our model CYCLE and SpEL model, calculated as $\text{Boost} = \frac{\text{Our Model's Result} - \text{SpEL Model's Result}}{\text{SpEL Model's Result}}$.

Table S15 and Table S17 show models' performance on the "Only Forward" setting. "Only Forward" means the results include only one scenario: the model is trained in the past and tested in the future. Table S16 and Table S18 show models' performance on the "Forward and Backward" setting. "Forward and Backward" means the results include two scenarios: training in the past and testing in the future, and training in the future and testing in the past. It is worth noting that when the gap is 0, it means the training and testing datasets come from the same year. Thus, the "Only Forward" and "Forward and Backward" values are equal.

Table S15. Temporal degradation mitigation performance on the "Only Forward" setting using "Graph-TempEL: New entities" as training dataset.

		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
@1	BLINK	0.1333	0.1339	0.1339	0.1356	0.1350	0.1361	0.1349	0.1358	0.1346	0.1430
	SpEL	0.1733	0.1695	0.1765	0.1771	0.1699	0.1720	0.1723	0.1790	0.1796	0.1933
	CYCLE	0.1930	0.1964	0.1976	0.2028	0.2001	0.2063	0.2070	0.2111	0.2108	0.2237
	Boost (%)	11.37%	15.84%	11.98%	14.48%	17.76%	19.91%	20.12%	17.89%	17.40%	15.73%
@2	BLINK	0.1995	0.1999	0.2004	0.2022	0.2015	0.2028	0.2010	0.2016	0.1999	0.2115
	SpEL	0.2444	0.2455	0.2504	0.2535	0.2513	0.2447	0.2484	0.2481	0.2496	0.2617
	CYCLE	0.2845	0.2898	0.2896	0.2993	0.2949	0.3036	0.3013	0.2997	0.3026	0.3230
	Boost (%)	16.42%	18.05%	15.69%	18.05%	17.36%	24.11%	21.26%	20.81%	21.24%	23.42%
@4	BLINK	0.2795	0.2789	0.2804	0.2825	0.2810	0.2837	0.2803	0.2813	0.2786	0.2951
	SpEL	0.3324	0.3411	0.3379	0.3396	0.3425	0.3457	0.3402	0.3446	0.3385	0.3652
	CYCLE	0.3876	0.3924	0.3926	0.4005	0.3947	0.4029	0.3998	0.3984	0.4006	0.4251
	Boost (%)	16.60%	15.03%	16.19%	17.93%	15.24%	16.56%	17.51%	15.61%	18.35%	16.40%
@8	BLINK	0.3721	0.3717	0.3735	0.3753	0.3725	0.3745	0.3714	0.3712	0.3684	0.3881
	SpEL	0.4370	0.4439	0.4422	0.4437	0.4424	0.4445	0.4438	0.4380	0.4437	0.4483
	CYCLE	0.5047	0.5099	0.5106	0.5218	0.5170	0.5295	0.5252	0.5234	0.5181	0.5400
	Boost (%)	15.49%	14.88%	15.46%	17.58%	16.86%	19.12%	18.32%	19.50%	16.76%	20.46%
@16	BLINK	0.4718	0.4717	0.4725	0.4738	0.4707	0.4729	0.4693	0.4680	0.4663	0.4850
	SpEL	0.5437	0.5427	0.5499	0.5452	0.5422	0.5448	0.5368	0.5415	0.5360	0.5448
	CYCLE	0.6066	0.6112	0.6112	0.6199	0.6157	0.6273	0.6260	0.6230	0.6154	0.6377
	Boost (%)	11.56%	12.62%	11.15%	13.71%	13.56%	15.14%	16.62%	15.06%	14.81%	17.05%
@32	BLINK	0.5749	0.5746	0.5742	0.5751	0.5716	0.5738	0.5695	0.5679	0.5655	0.5854
	SpEL	0.6407	0.6412	0.6393	0.6451	0.6398	0.6397	0.6371	0.6345	0.6352	0.6555
	CYCLE	0.7016	0.7056	0.7045	0.7119	0.7085	0.7175	0.7154	0.7155	0.7126	0.7326
	Boost (%)	9.50%	10.05%	10.20%	10.36%	10.73%	12.16%	12.29%	12.76%	12.19%	11.76%
@64	BLINK	0.6742	0.6739	0.6735	0.6743	0.6712	0.6734	0.6698	0.6671	0.6652	0.6833
	SpEL	0.7331	0.7350	0.7310	0.7370	0.7279	0.7354	0.7323	0.7270	0.7201	0.7432
	CYCLE	0.7877	0.7895	0.7886	0.7941	0.7920	0.7978	0.7971	0.7936	0.7861	0.8124
	Boost (%)	7.45%	7.41%	7.88%	7.75%	8.81%	8.49%	8.85%	9.16%	9.17%	9.31%

Table S16. Temporal degradation mitigation performance on the "Forward and Backward" setting using "Graph-TempEL: New entities" as training dataset.

		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
@1	BLINK	0.1333	0.1326	0.1331	0.1333	0.1330	0.1326	0.1322	0.1306	0.1306	0.1349
	SpEL	0.1733	0.1687	0.1737	0.1725	0.1688	0.1685	0.1709	0.1672	0.1731	0.1750
	CYCLE	0.1930	0.1929	0.1927	0.1932	0.1902	0.1912	0.1921	0.1906	0.1921	0.1889
	Boost (%)	11.37%	14.32%	10.91%	12.01%	12.69%	13.47%	12.45%	13.99%	10.96%	7.97%
@2	BLINK	0.1995	0.1985	0.1993	0.1997	0.1991	0.1983	0.1973	0.1958	0.1956	0.2014
	SpEL	0.2444	0.2457	0.2461	0.2482	0.2465	0.2401	0.2423	0.2390	0.2430	0.2365
	CYCLE	0.2845	0.2843	0.2842	0.2877	0.2824	0.2828	0.2824	0.2746	0.2805	0.2746
	Boost (%)	16.42%	15.69%	15.49%	15.93%	14.59%	17.77%	16.55%	14.90%	15.47%	16.11%
@4	BLINK	0.2795	0.2777	0.2794	0.2797	0.2788	0.2787	0.2771	0.2749	0.2743	0.2829
	SpEL	0.3324	0.3344	0.3356	0.3354	0.3404	0.3387	0.3321	0.3298	0.3266	0.3380
	CYCLE	0.3876	0.3879	0.3874	0.3915	0.3860	0.3854	0.3857	0.3782	0.3814	0.3789
	Boost (%)	16.60%	16.00%	15.46%	16.74%	13.41%	13.81%	16.14%	14.70%	16.80%	12.10%
@8	BLINK	0.3721	0.3704	0.3721	0.3732	0.3714	0.3708	0.3692	0.3653	0.3651	0.3749
	SpEL	0.4370	0.4398	0.4421	0.4409	0.4388	0.4398	0.4354	0.4319	0.4277	0.4201
	CYCLE	0.5047	0.5051	0.5048	0.5087	0.5021	0.5032	0.5027	0.4938	0.4962	0.4908
	Boost (%)	15.49%	14.85%	14.20%	15.38%	14.44%	14.41%	15.45%	14.33%	16.00%	16.83%
@16	BLINK	0.4718	0.4703	0.4721	0.4727	0.4710	0.4703	0.4689	0.4643	0.4645	0.4726
	SpEL	0.5437	0.5402	0.5414	0.5419	0.5392	0.5383	0.5364	0.5309	0.5294	0.5274
	CYCLE	0.6066	0.6065	0.6069	0.6085	0.6026	0.6057	0.6064	0.5973	0.5973	0.5937
	Boost (%)	11.56%	12.27%	12.10%	12.28%	11.75%	12.52%	13.05%	12.51%	12.83%	12.56%
@32	BLINK	0.5749	0.5731	0.5745	0.5748	0.5729	0.5724	0.5711	0.5660	0.5659	0.5745
	SpEL	0.6407	0.6419	0.6420	0.6441	0.6412	0.6393	0.6336	0.6309	0.6332	0.6395
	CYCLE	0.7016	0.7014	0.7010	0.7029	0.6993	0.6997	0.7019	0.6955	0.6975	0.6933
	Boost (%)	9.50%	9.27%	9.19%	9.13%	9.06%	9.46%	10.78%	10.23%	10.16%	8.41%
@64	BLINK	0.6742	0.6731	0.6741	0.6749	0.6733	0.6730	0.6723	0.6675	0.6665	0.6737
	SpEL	0.7331	0.7320	0.7316	0.7348	0.7307	0.7320	0.7311	0.7257	0.7190	0.7186
	CYCLE	0.7877	0.7867	0.7875	0.7884	0.7857	0.7865	0.7878	0.7819	0.7807	0.7856
	Boost (%)	7.45%	7.48%	7.64%	7.31%	7.53%	7.46%	7.76%	7.74%	8.58%	9.33%

Table S17. Temporal degradation mitigation performance on the "Only Forward" setting using "Graph-TempEL: Continual entities" as training dataset.

		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
@1	BLINK	0.1760	0.1770	0.1776	0.1767	0.1755	0.1755	0.1703	0.1764	0.1682	0.1741
	SpEL	0.2289	0.2266	0.2247	0.2215	0.2273	0.2243	0.2245	0.2264	0.2183	0.2264
	CYCLE	0.2832	0.2833	0.2852	0.2842	0.2807	0.2789	0.2696	0.2653	0.2590	0.2537
	Boost (%)	23.76%	25.03%	26.93%	28.33%	23.47%	24.32%	20.07%	17.17%	18.64%	12.06%
@2	BLINK	0.2586	0.2600	0.2608	0.2596	0.2589	0.2577	0.2509	0.2575	0.2482	0.2551
	SpEL	0.3186	0.3185	0.3189	0.3194	0.3193	0.3186	0.3118	0.3162	0.3144	0.3124
	CYCLE	0.3965	0.3971	0.3973	0.3960	0.3925	0.3880	0.3807	0.3721	0.3720	0.3688
	Boost (%)	24.45%	24.70%	24.59%	23.98%	22.94%	21.79%	22.08%	17.70%	18.32%	18.05%
@4	BLINK	0.3548	0.3568	0.3569	0.3552	0.3544	0.3526	0.3459	0.3536	0.3441	0.3522
	SpEL	0.4238	0.4262	0.4254	0.4256	0.4259	0.4214	0.4081	0.4202	0.4065	0.4320
	CYCLE	0.5137	0.5142	0.5147	0.5141	0.5089	0.5034	0.4953	0.4852	0.4786	0.4691
	Boost (%)	21.19%	20.64%	20.98%	20.80%	19.49%	19.46%	21.39%	15.48%	17.74%	8.59%
@8	BLINK	0.4594	0.4617	0.4622	0.4601	0.4585	0.4575	0.4496	0.4581	0.4501	0.4564
	SpEL	0.5394	0.5421	0.5448	0.5372	0.5362	0.5352	0.5299	0.5403	0.5281	0.5383
	CYCLE	0.6226	0.6245	0.6243	0.6216	0.6175	0.6166	0.6078	0.6002	0.5950	0.5942
	Boost (%)	15.41%	15.21%	14.58%	15.72%	15.16%	15.21%	14.69%	11.08%	12.68%	10.38%
@16	BLINK	0.5668	0.5689	0.5695	0.5683	0.5658	0.5647	0.5571	0.5647	0.5570	0.5640
	SpEL	0.6382	0.6369	0.6420	0.6391	0.6344	0.6335	0.6297	0.6358	0.6214	0.6422
	CYCLE	0.7177	0.7177	0.7185	0.7174	0.7175	0.7154	0.7120	0.7037	0.7010	0.6980
	Boost (%)	12.45%	12.69%	11.92%	12.25%	13.11%	12.93%	13.07%	10.68%	12.80%	8.69%
@32	BLINK	0.6717	0.6729	0.6735	0.6724	0.6699	0.6691	0.6624	0.6687	0.6615	0.6684
	SpEL	0.7308	0.7318	0.7305	0.7351	0.7331	0.7231	0.7213	0.7307	0.7209	0.7208
	CYCLE	0.8068	0.8066	0.8068	0.8052	0.8035	0.8020	0.7982	0.7905	0.7846	0.7905
	Boost (%)	10.40%	10.22%	10.45%	9.53%	9.60%	10.92%	10.66%	8.19%	8.84%	9.67%
@64	BLINK	0.7666	0.7676	0.7681	0.7664	0.7647	0.7640	0.7594	0.7649	0.7595	0.7639
	SpEL	0.8169	0.8181	0.8197	0.8149	0.8185	0.8155	0.8090	0.8166	0.8123	0.8096
	CYCLE	0.8669	0.8667	0.8662	0.8655	0.8637	0.8614	0.8568	0.8548	0.8550	0.8544
	Boost (%)	6.12%	5.94%	5.67%	6.21%	5.51%	5.63%	5.91%	4.68%	5.25%	5.53%

Table S18. Temporal degradation mitigation performance on the "Forward and Backward" setting using "Graph-TempEL: Continual entities" as training dataset.

		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
@1	BLINK	0.1760	0.1765	0.1779	0.1766	0.1775	0.1764	0.1731	0.1755	0.1691	0.1682
	SpEL	0.2289	0.2266	0.2268	0.2254	0.2286	0.2246	0.2260	0.2249	0.2214	0.2232
	CYCLE	0.2832	0.2848	0.2866	0.2867	0.2853	0.2817	0.2759	0.2716	0.2666	0.2650
	Boost (%)	23.76%	25.66%	26.37%	27.19%	24.81%	25.40%	22.05%	20.78%	20.43%	18.73%
@2	BLINK	0.2586	0.2592	0.2610	0.2591	0.2613	0.2586	0.2549	0.2576	0.2494	0.2487
	SpEL	0.3186	0.3190	0.3212	0.3185	0.3205	0.3190	0.3154	0.3151	0.3092	0.3094
	CYCLE	0.3965	0.3982	0.3993	0.4006	0.3985	0.3955	0.3900	0.3842	0.3816	0.3765
	Boost (%)	24.45%	24.81%	24.33%	25.75%	24.33%	24.01%	23.65%	21.94%	23.41%	21.71%
@4	BLINK	0.3548	0.3555	0.3572	0.3554	0.3580	0.3545	0.3502	0.3537	0.3446	0.3437
	SpEL	0.4238	0.4257	0.4267	0.4275	0.4286	0.4244	0.4155	0.4200	0.4142	0.4193
	CYCLE	0.5137	0.5164	0.5171	0.5181	0.5156	0.5115	0.5055	0.4964	0.4925	0.4872
	Boost (%)	21.19%	21.31%	21.21%	21.20%	20.31%	20.53%	21.66%	18.20%	18.89%	16.21%
@8	BLINK	0.4594	0.4607	0.4623	0.4600	0.4626	0.4597	0.4547	0.4577	0.4494	0.4480
	SpEL	0.5394	0.5419	0.5425	0.5406	0.5409	0.5394	0.5357	0.5375	0.5265	0.5244
	CYCLE	0.6226	0.6258	0.6258	0.6253	0.6234	0.6203	0.6165	0.6095	0.6051	0.6022
	Boost (%)	15.41%	15.49%	15.34%	15.67%	15.24%	15.00%	15.07%	13.38%	14.93%	14.83%
@16	BLINK	0.5668	0.5679	0.5696	0.5680	0.5696	0.5670	0.5623	0.5647	0.5568	0.5553
	SpEL	0.6382	0.6362	0.6385	0.6359	0.6388	0.6366	0.6338	0.6363	0.6249	0.6307
	CYCLE	0.7177	0.7187	0.7189	0.7191	0.7178	0.7156	0.7126	0.7083	0.7076	0.7084
	Boost (%)	12.45%	12.98%	12.59%	13.07%	12.37%	12.41%	12.43%	11.32%	13.23%	12.33%
@32	BLINK	0.6717	0.6721	0.6737	0.6724	0.6734	0.6709	0.6667	0.6691	0.6612	0.6610
	SpEL	0.7308	0.7320	0.7315	0.7315	0.7316	0.7265	0.7245	0.7299	0.7237	0.7205
	CYCLE	0.8068	0.8075	0.8083	0.8080	0.8059	0.8043	0.8013	0.7966	0.7922	0.7930
	Boost (%)	10.40%	10.32%	10.50%	10.46%	10.16%	10.70%	10.61%	9.14%	9.47%	10.06%
@64	BLINK	0.7666	0.7670	0.7681	0.7669	0.7678	0.7661	0.7630	0.7651	0.7594	0.7573
	SpEL	0.8169	0.8172	0.8197	0.8177	0.8204	0.8187	0.8129	0.8120	0.8125	0.8048
	CYCLE	0.8669	0.8677	0.8678	0.8685	0.8678	0.8657	0.8628	0.8603	0.8606	0.8604
	Boost (%)	6.12%	6.19%	5.87%	6.22%	5.77%	5.75%	6.15%	5.95%	5.93%	6.90%

4. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT MODELS

It is also worth noting that the improvement effect of our model diminishes gradually as the metric threshold shifts from @1 to @64, as shown in Figure S1. The x-axis denotes the year gap between training and testing datasets, and the y-axis represents the improvement margin of our model compared to the SpEL model. The solid line represents the model trained on "Graph-TempEL: New Entities," while the dashed line indicates the model trained on "Graph-TempEL: Continual Entities."

(a) Only Forward

(b) Forward and Backward

Fig. S1. Different of Recall changes as the metric changes.